

METHODOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES ON DEVELOPING STUDENTS' METACOGNITIVE COMPETENCES

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Abstract

The article explores the importance of developing metacognitive abilities in university students, from the perspective of instructional methodologies oriented toward self-regulated learning. In the transition from traditional knowledge-transmission models to constructivist and reflective paradigms, metacognition emerges as a key competence in both professional and personal development. The paper examines the main theoretical frameworks concerning the structure and functions of metacognition (declarative, procedural, and conditional knowledge) and its relationship with self-regulated learning. From a methodological standpoint, it presents teaching strategies and formative tools that foster awareness of cognitive processes: reflective journals, learning portfolios,

formative self-assessment, metacognitive feedback, and collaborative technology-supported activities. The analysis highlights the role of the university teacher as a facilitator of reflection and learning autonomy. Conclusions emphasize the need for systematically integrating metacognitive competencies into the university curriculum to cultivate a self-regulated learner profile capable of planning, monitoring, and evaluating one's own learning process.

Keywords: metacognition, self-regulated learning, reflection, higher education, metacognitive strategies

1. Introduction

In recent decades, transformations in higher education brought about by socio-economic, technological, and cultural changes have led to a gradual shift from the accumulation of declarative knowledge to the development of complex, transferable, and adaptable skills necessary for professional and social integration. In this context, universities, through their academic content, train autonomous students who are capable of managing their own long-term learning process.

This reorientation is supported by European educational policies, which promote an educational paradigm centered on students, learning outcomes, and the development of transversal skills. Strategic documents support the need to develop skills such as critical thinking, self-assessment, autonomy in learning, and responsibility for one's own educational path. These skills can be developed effectively in the presence of higher-order cognitive processes that allow students to plan, monitor, and evaluate their own learning efforts.

In this context, metacognition emerges as a key competence, playing a central role in supporting autonomous and self-regulated learning. Broadly defined as reflection on one's own cognitive processes, metacognition allows individuals to become aware of how they learn, identify effective strategies, and

adjust their cognitive approaches according to the task and context. Research in the field shows that students with a high level of metacognitive awareness demonstrate superior academic performance, a higher degree of autonomy, and a greater ability to transfer learning to new contexts.

However, in practice, there are many situations in which university education continues to be marked by traditional teaching models, focused on the unilateral transmission of information and privileging the final result of learning, to the detriment of the process, offering few opportunities for reflection, self-assessment, and self-regulation. In contrast, constructivist and socio-constructivist approaches promote active learning, student involvement in meaning-making, and the value of reflection as a tool for cognitive and professional development.

In the field of teacher training, including pedagogical specializations, future professionals must not only master specialized content, but also develop reflective skills necessary to adapt to diverse educational situations. Without explicit metacognitive training, students risk reproducing transmissive models in their teaching practice, thus limiting the formative potential of the educational process.

In pedagogical specializations, including in the field of teacher training, future professionals must not only master specialized content, but also develop reflective skills necessary to adapt to the diversity of educational situations. In the absence of explicit metacognitive training, students risk subsequently reproducing transmissive models in their teaching practice, thus limiting the formative potential of the educational process.

The specific objectives of the article are:

- highlighting the role of metacognition in supporting autonomous learning and lifelong learning skills;

- analyzing the main theoretical models that explain the structure and functions of metacognition in educational contexts;
- exploring formative strategies and tools that promote the development of metacognitive skills.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. Conceptualizing metacognition: definitions and structural components

Metacognition has evolved significantly as a field of research in recent decades and is now considered a fundamental construct for self-regulated learning, academic performance, and professional development. The term was officially introduced by J. H. Flavell, who defined metacognition as "knowledge about cognitive phenomena" (Flavell, 1979), emphasizing that individuals can take into account their own cognitive processes and their products. In earlier works, Flavell outlines the essential dimensions of metacognition by introducing the concepts of cognitive monitoring and control (Flavell, 1976), suggesting that metacognition involves the active evaluation and organization of cognitive processes to achieve specific goals.

Subsequently, the literature has significantly expanded the scope of the term. A. L. Brown (1978, 1980) proposes a structured dichotomy in metacognitive knowledge—comprising declarative, procedural, and conditional knowledge—and metacognitive regulation, which includes planning, monitoring, and evaluation processes. This structure has proven useful in subsequent research on self-regulation of the learning process.

These components are now considered standard elements of metacognitive architecture, as shown by the models synthesized in recent literature. One example is the Good Information Processing Model (Pressley, Borkowski & Schneider, 1989), which positions metacognition in an

interdependent system of knowledge, motivation, strategies, and situational factors, affirming the cyclical and developable nature of the process (Schneider, 2008; Borkowski & Muthukrishna, 1992).

In the same vein, contemporary pedagogical research has attempted to further refine the construct. Metacognition is a multidimensional concept, difficult to define, but central to professional self-regulation, interconnecting monitoring, control, and self-regulation in the self-management of personal development. The operational definition of metacognition has not strayed far from its original meaning, with researchers agreeing that metacognition plays an essential role in monitoring and developing cognitive processes (Aldea, 2022).

In addition to these cognitive and pedagogical perspectives, Manzoor and Petukhova (2022) introduce the perspective of metacognitive experiences, emphasizing the situational and affective components of metacognition in the context of decision-making and collaborative learning, which broadens the conceptual framework from simple intrapsychic processes to complex adaptive interactions.

In conclusion, there is a theoretical convergence on the fact that metacognition simultaneously includes: knowledge about cognition, regulation of cognition, and metacognitive experiences. These components explain why metacognition is essential not only in academic learning, but also in professional, decision-making, and socio-cognitive contexts.

2.2. Metacognition and Self-Regulated Learning

Metacognition is now considered a central pillar of self-regulated learning (SRL). In a classic model, Zimmerman defines SRL as an active process in which "learners set goals for learning and then attempt to monitor, regulate, and control their cognition, motivation, and behavior" (Pintrich, 2000, p. 453), emphasizing

the integration of cognitive components with motivational and metacognitive ones.

Modern integrative models have explained not only the internal architecture of metacognition, but also its relationship to educational performance. One such example is the MASRL Model - "metacognitive and affective model of self-regulated learning" (Efklides, 2008), widely used in current research. The model distinguishes between: (a) Person Level — where metacognition is related to traits, profiles, and beliefs, and (b) Task × Person Level — where strategies and processes appear context-dependent. MASRL is a valuable model in the training of future primary and preschool teachers because it allows for the design of differentiated interventions at the level of strategy, reflection, and self-regulation (Aldea, 2023).

Metacognition interact significantly with motivational components, especially with self-efficacy, a concept developed by Bandura. Schunk (1996, 2008) highlights the link between metacognition and self-efficacy, arguing that monitoring and self-assessment of performance generate internal feedback about competence, influencing persistence, effort, and self-regulation. Thus, self-efficacy becomes a mediator between metacognition and performance.

Over the past two decades, educational literature has shifted its focus from simple metacognitive strategies to the systematic training of the SRL profile. Thus, in practical terms, these studies support several key ideas:

- metacognition is the structural condition for self-regulation,
- without metacognitive components there is no complete SRL profile,
- metacognitive transfer is possible and useful in disciplinary and professional contexts,

- educational interventions can increase the level of SRL through deliberate instruction.

2.3. Metacognition and Lifelong Learning Competence

In academic and professional contexts, metacognition is now linked to the lifelong learning paradigm, where the focus has shifted from the accumulation of knowledge to the development of reflective and self-regulated learning skills. Key competencies assign metacognition an explicit role in the development of critical thinking, learning management, professional self-orientation, and adaptability. In educational terms, this translates into the student's ability to plan, monitor, and evaluate the autonomous learning process in order to cope with emerging professional situations.

Recent research highlights that professionals with a developed metacognitive profile demonstrate: autonomy in learning, reflective thinking, long-term planning skills, resilience in changing contexts, and the ability to transfer knowledge between domains.

These characteristics justify the integration of metacognition into the university curriculum as a cross-cutting meta-competence, with a role in the sustainability of personal and professional development.

2.4. Metacognition as a cyclical process of Self-Regulated Learning

Contemporary theories of learning increasingly conceptualize metacognition not as a static set of skills, but as a cyclical, self-regulatory process through which students actively plan, monitor, and evaluate their cognitive activity. This perspective aligns metacognition with self-regulated learning (SRL) models, which describe learning as an interactive process shaped by continuous feedback between cognition, motivation, and reflection (Zimmerman, 2002; Pintrich, 2004).

From this perspective, metacognition functions as an executive mechanism that allows students to move from passive information processing to intentional control of learning. The cyclical nature of this process is particularly well illustrated by models that integrate internal metacognitive regulation with external instructional support, emphasizing the dynamic interaction between the student and the learning environment. Thus, metacognition can be understood as a cyclical process of self-regulated learning that involves planning, performance monitoring, and self-reflection (Zimmerman, 2002). This cycle of internal regulation interacts with external instructional structures that support conceptual change.

The cyclical process of metacognition involves three interconnected phases: prediction (planning), performance control (monitoring), and self-reflection (evaluation). These phases do not occur linearly, but form a recursive loop in which each phase develops and reshapes the others.

- Planning refers to the anticipatory phase of learning, during which students activate prior knowledge, set goals, and select strategies. At this stage, metacognitive knowledge plays a crucial role, as students rely on their understanding of their own knowledge, the task, and the available strategies to make informed decisions.
- Performance monitoring involves real-time monitoring of cognitive activity during task completion. Students assess their level of understanding, regulate their attention and effort, and adjust their strategies based on perceived difficulties. This phase reflects the active control dimension of metacognition.
- Self-reflection occurs after task completion and includes evaluating outcomes, strategies, and learning processes. Through

reflection, students analyze the effectiveness of their approaches and generate ideas that influence future learning cycles.

Together, these phases constitute the central regulatory loop of self-regulated learning, positioning metacognition as a process that continuously shapes and reshapes learning behavior.

Figure 1: Metacognition as a cyclical process of self-regulated learning and conceptual change (adapted from Zimmerman, 2002; Posner et al., 1982).

The cyclical nature of metacognition and its role in self-regulated learning are summarized in Figure 1, which illustrates the interaction between internal metacognitive processes and external instructional schemes in supporting conceptual change and learning development. The student starts from a pre-existing idea, which represents prior knowledge, beliefs, or conceptions. Internal metacognitive processes—prediction, performance monitoring, and self-reflection—operate within this cognitive space, guiding how students interact with new information. These processes are governed by reflective criteria, such

as intelligibility, plausibility, and broad applicability, which function as metacognitive standards for assessing understanding.

- Intelligibility refers to whether new information is understood.
- Plausibility refers to whether information is perceived as coherent and credible.
- Broad applicability refers to the extent to which the new idea can be transferred and applied in different contexts.

When these criteria are met, students are able to revise or reconstruct their prior knowledge, resulting in new or revised ideas. In this sense, metacognition mediates conceptual change, allowing students to move from superficial acceptance of information to deeper understanding.

A key contribution of the model illustrated in Figure 1 is the explicit inclusion of external factors that support metacognitive regulation. These factors—such as attention to prior knowledge, engagement with content, formative assessment, and responsive feedback—do not replace internal regulation, but rather support it.

Instructional supports, including reflection questions, feedback requests, and assessment criteria, lead to the externalization of metacognitive processes and make them accessible to students. By guiding attention, stimulating reflection, and providing feedback, these supports improve students' abilities to regulate their cognitive processes autonomously. The model also emphasizes that effective learning results from the interaction between internal regulation and external support, rather than from either component alone.

Metacognition becomes a fundamental mechanism of self-regulated learning by integrating internal cognitive control with external instructional schemas. Cognitive strategies determine how information is processed, motivational factors influence effort and perseverance, but metacognition

coordinates these elements, allowing learners to decide when, why, and how to act.

This perspective has significant implications for higher education, where students are expected to take on increasing responsibility for their own learning. Viewing metacognition as a cyclical process highlights the importance of designing learning environments that encourage reflection, monitoring, and evaluation, thereby supporting the development of autonomous and self-regulated learners.

This cyclical model of metacognition highlights learning as an adaptive and reflective process, in which prior knowledge is continuously revised through self-regulation and instructional support. In interaction with motivation and self-regulation, metacognition supports performance, transfer, and self-development, integrating into the paradigm of self-regulated learning and lifelong learning, with direct implications for university education and career management.

3. Methodological perspectives on developing students' metacognitive competences

In higher education, it is necessary to move beyond the traditional paradigm centered on knowledge transfer and adopt pedagogical approaches oriented towards active, reflective, and self-regulated learning. In this context, the development of metacognitive skills cannot be conceived as a collateral result of teaching, but rather integrated into the curricular and methodological design.

Research shows that simply exposing students to academic content and tasks does not lead to the emergence of metacognitive processes (Efklides, 2008). Metacognition requires deliberate learning situations that require planning, monitoring, and evaluation of cognitive activity. Self-regulation models emphasize that students become aware of their own learning processes only when

they are actively involved in decisions about goals, strategies, and criteria for success (Pintrich, 2000).

In this context, activities focused on guided reflection and formative feedback significantly increase the level of metacognitive awareness and autonomy in learning (Schunk, 2008). Students learn effectively when they are required to explain their own reasoning, analyze errors, and reflect on the strategies they have used. From a methodological perspective, this involves designing activities that promote: problem-solving, discovery learning, project-based learning, and collaborative learning.

Research on the transfer of metacognitive skills shows that these approaches are effective when combined with explicit instruction on metacognitive strategies. Guided discussions, peer feedback, and collaborative activities facilitate the verbalization of cognitive processes and the comparison of strategies used, contributing to the development of metacognitive awareness. Thus, metacognition is not only an individual process, but also a socially mediated one, which can be systematically developed through the use of specific strategies, coherently integrated into teaching activities:

- **Reflective journals** are a valuable tool for stimulating self-analysis and monitoring the learning process. By reflecting on the difficulties encountered, the strategies used, and the progress made, students are encouraged to build a clear representation of their own cognitive processes. The use of reflective journals contributes to the consolidation of metacognitive knowledge and the development of self-assessment skills.

- **Learning portfolios.** The portfolio is considered a complex formative assessment tool that supports the development of metacognitive skills by integrating reflection, selection, and justification of academic

products. In a university context, portfolios allow for the monitoring of medium- and long-term progress and facilitate the correlation of learning objectives with the results obtained. Portfolios promote self-regulation and student accountability for their own learning path.

- **Self-assessment and peer assessment** are essential strategies for developing critical performance evaluation skills. By referring to explicit criteria and performance standards, students develop metacognitive analysis skills and adjust their learning strategies. Schunk (1996) emphasizes that accurate self-assessment is closely linked to the development of self-efficacy, which in turn supports self-regulation and persistence in the task.

- **Metacognitive feedback.** Feedback with a metacognitive function goes beyond simply correcting products and focuses on processes: how the task was approached, why a strategy was effective or not, and what alternatives can be used. Process-oriented feedback is more effective than feedback focused exclusively on results, as it supports the development of the ability to monitor and adjust learning strategies (Schunk, 2008).

- **Technology-supported and collaborative metacognitive learning.** Integrating technology into university education offers significant opportunities to support metacognitive learning. LMS platforms, collaborative tools, and interactive digital media can facilitate reflection, rapid feedback, and progress monitoring. The use of digital media becomes effective from a metacognitive perspective when accompanied by intentional pedagogical design. Digital tools do not automatically develop metacognition, but must be used to support activities such as reflective journaling, formative assessment, and structured collaboration. In this sense, we can emphasize the importance of training

metacognitive skills in virtual contexts, highlighting the role of the teacher as a mediator of reflection (Manasia, 2020).

Furthermore, technology-assisted collaborative activities allow for the externalization of thinking and the comparison of strategies used by different students, contributing to the development of social metacognition and the consolidation of self-regulation in learning groups.

4. Role of the university teacher in fostering metacognition

The development of metacognitive skills in higher education depends on the role assumed by university teachers; metacognition requires intentional pedagogical mediation, curricular coherence, and an institutional climate conducive to reflection and self-regulation (Efklides, 2008; Schunk, 2008). In this context, the teacher becomes a key player in designing, facilitating, and evaluating students' metacognitive processes.

According to self-regulated learning theories, the teacher is perceived as a designer of learning experiences who supports students in formulating goals, choosing strategies, and evaluating progress (Zimmerman, 2002; Pintrich, 2004). As Schunk (2008) points out, effective instruction involves creating contexts in which students become "active seekers and processors of information," capable of reflecting on their own learning decisions.

From a metacognitive perspective, the role of the teacher is redefined as a facilitator of reflection, who: verbalizes cognitive processes (modeling), explains the steps to success, encourages self-questioning and self-regulation, and normalizes error as a source of learning. This paradigm shift is also supported by Veenman and his collaborators (2006), who show that students exposed to reflective teaching practices develop higher levels of metacognitive awareness and autonomy in learning.

Developing metacognitive skills in higher education requires the intentional design of learning situations that activate students' awareness of their cognitive processes and support their capacity for self-regulated learning. Metacognition and self-regulated learning are closely interrelated concepts, as metacognitive knowledge enables students to understand cognitive functioning, while self-regulated learning provides the mechanisms by which they plan, monitor, and regulate their actions (Zimmerman, 2002; Efklides, 2008). Consequently, educational practices that explicitly integrate metacognitive strategies can significantly enhance students' autonomy, reflective thinking, and professional competence.

From a methodological perspective, effective learning situations involve structured opportunities for planning, monitoring, and reflection, allowing learners to consciously regulate their learning process. This interaction between metacognition and self-regulation can be operationalized through authentic tasks, reflective prompts, and formative feedback, which guide learners in evaluating and adjusting their strategies (Pintrich, 2004; Nicol & Macfarlane-Dick, 2006).

The interaction between metacognitive knowledge, strategy selection, and regulation processes can be illustrated by cyclical models of self-regulated learning, which emphasize the dynamic relationship between awareness, monitoring, and strategy adjustment. Metacognitive knowledge supports strategy selection and monitoring processes, enabling learners to effectively regulate their learning process (Figure 2).

J. Adam Hickey, Landmark Outreach © 2007

Figure 2. Metacognitive knowledge and strategy regulation cycle in self-regulated learning (adapted from Hickey, 2007).

Metacognition and self-regulated learning function as complementary processes in student development: metacognition provides the cognitive awareness necessary to understand learning processes, while self-regulated learning allows students to apply this awareness through strategic planning, monitoring, and adjustment.

This interaction is important in the preparation of future teachers, as reflective and self-regulated students are better equipped to support children's cognitive and socio-emotional development. By experiencing metacognitive learning themselves, students develop the ability to design educational activities that promote reflection and autonomy in young learners. Therefore, integrating metacognitive strategies into teacher training programs is an essential component of preparing future educators capable of facilitating reflective and autonomous learning.

At the level of educational policy, European and international documents promote the development of transversal skills, including metacognition, as the foundation of lifelong learning.

5. Discussion

Theoretical and methodological analysis highlights a clear convergence between explanatory models of metacognition and educational practices oriented towards self-regulated learning. Classical and contemporary models of metacognition (Flavell; Brown; Efklides; Zimmerman) support the idea that metacognition is a functional structure, activated in educational contexts that require reflection, self-regulation, and student accountability for their own learning process.

From a methodological perspective, the formative strategies analyzed—reflective journals, portfolios, self-assessment, metacognitive feedback, and collaborative activities—can be interpreted as operational tools of metacognition, as they explicitly facilitate the processes of planning, monitoring, and evaluation. Thus, the theoretical dimension of metacognition is translated into concrete educational practices, consistent with the constructivist paradigm and self-regulated learning models.

The results of the analyzed research indicate that formative strategies have a significant impact on the development of metacognitive skills, especially when used systematically and explicitly. Reflective journals and learning portfolios promote awareness of the learning process, transforming the academic experience into an object of deliberate reflection. Self-assessment and process-oriented feedback contribute to the adjustment of cognitive strategies and the development of control over one's own performance.

The effectiveness of these strategies is explained by the fact that they shift the focus from the final learning outcome to the process of knowledge construction, stimulating self-regulation and self-monitoring. In this sense, formative strategies function as mediating mechanisms between the teacher's pedagogical intention and the development of the student's metacognitive skills.

At the same time, research on metacognitive transfer shows that strategies that include explicit instruction and guided reflection lead not only to improved immediate academic performance, but also to the transfer of metacognitive skills to new learning contexts. This is particularly relevant for higher education, where cognitive flexibility and adaptability are essential.

Metacognition is at the core of self-regulation, allowing students to set realistic goals, monitor their progress, and critically evaluate their results. Thus, self-regulated students are characterized by:

- the ability to plan learning strategically,
- the conscious use of cognitive strategies,
- continuous monitoring of understanding,
- reflective evaluation of performance,
- adjusting learning behavior based on feedback.

The development of this profile is not a spontaneous process, but the result of deliberate educational interventions that value metacognition as a tool for

cognitive and motivational control. Thus, metacognition can be interpreted as a metacompetence that supports the functioning of other academic and professional competences.

6. Conclusions

The article highlighted the central role of metacognition in the development of self-regulated learning and in the formation of the skills necessary for lifelong education. The theoretical analysis demonstrated that metacognition is a multidimensional structure that includes knowledge about cognition, regulation of cognitive processes, and metacognitive experiences, while the methodological analysis showed that these dimensions can be developed through formative and reflective educational strategies.

Based on the analysis, metacognitive competence can be argued to be a core competence in university education because:

- it supports the development of autonomy in learning;
- it facilitates the transfer of knowledge;
- it optimizes academic performance;
- it supports professional adaptability;
- it underpins lifelong learning.

In conclusion, metacognition is cross-cutting in nature, being relevant to all fields of study and educational levels, and is an essential element in training graduates who are capable of learning autonomously, reflexively, and responsibly in a constantly changing knowledge society.

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